

Rural assets enabling a wellbeing-focused economic recovery: an inventory to inform data collection and analysis

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Summary

- **In this report, we outline a framework for structuring data collection on the assets of rural areas, in order to improve our understanding of the Scottish rural economy and its diversity. This framework will inform our analysis, which will include advanced modelling of rural development.**
- **Assets are resources of places and their people which can benefit communities and businesses. It is critical to understand access to a broad range of assets, in order to meaningfully reduce inequalities and support a wellbeing economy.**
- **Stakeholders and practitioners engaged in rural economic development in Scotland have contributed valuable expertise to workshops discussing the assets required to enable a wellbeing-focused recovery in rural and island communities.**
- **The list of assets emphasises the importance of a broad-based understanding of the economy and the contributions of human and social capital to this. Assets highlighted include tangible features and infrastructure, as well as the factors and strengths which enable the use of other assets and support rural development more broadly.**
- **The next stage of our research is to convert the assets inventory into a detailed database, supporting further analysis and modelling and generating fresh understanding of changing patterns of rural development and spatial inequalities.**

Background: The Scottish Government funds a programme of strategic research through the Rural and Environment Science and Analytical Services (RESAS) Division to advance the evidence base in the development of rural affairs, food and environment policies.

One of the themes of the research programme is on Rural Futures. This theme has three research topics: rural communities, rural economy and land reform. There are two projects within each topic led by Scotland's Rural College and the James Hutton Institute. This publication sits within this theme. Within the rural economy topic, the two projects are:

- *Informing a socially and spatially just future for the Scottish rural economy: pinpointing opportunities, assets and support needs*
- *Novel insights on Scotland's rural and island economies*

The first project, led by the James Hutton Institute, aims to use mixed methods to create an advanced, holistic understanding of the Scottish rural economy and the diversity of responses to multiple crises and events across rural Scotland, in the context of national objectives to deliver a wellbeing economy and longer-term challenges of inequality and depopulation. We aim to identify and inform better interventions and approaches to local development which can enable positive changes in communities. This project will produce evidence, including written publications, open datasets, and online material available to all.

Introduction

This report summarises a proposed framework which can be used to structure the collection of quantitative and spatial data within research on Scotland's rural and island economies which is being carried out from 2022-27, and which benefits from mutually supportive links with Hutton-led research on rural communities (in the project "Realising change: working with communities to inform a resilient recovery process in remote, rural and island communities"). We can describe this as an 'assets inventory', reflecting our interest in the links between the diverse resources of places and people (which if accessed and used effectively, can benefit local businesses and communities), and outcomes in the same places. The latter could include more universal goals of policies and strategies affecting rural Scotland, including supporting good quality jobs and balanced populations, alongside more specific place-based, community-driven targets for local development. We aim to produce new evidence on changing distributions of assets over time for localities, and analyse how these align with changes to local economies and communities. In addition to forming valuable analysis in its own right, our research aspires to integrate this with novel learning about economic decision-making and advanced modelling, supported by understanding of emerging changes within communities through co-designed activities in case studies.

Why should we be interested in assets? Rationale for using this approach

When engaging with practitioners and stakeholders within this project, we defined assets as "the resources that characterise a place and the people that live there, which can benefit the local community and businesses in some way". There are several reasons, informed by literature, policies, and challenges in measuring rural development, why using a broad definition of assets, and measuring differences in access to these, is a valuable framing within our project. Firstly, there is recognition that the UK as a whole "is one of the most regionally unbalanced countries in the industrialized world" (McCann, 2020: 256), but there is also understanding that 'left behind' places are found in many types of area (Martin et al., 2021) and that inequalities are complex (Patias et al., 2022). In Scotland, there is a growing prioritisation of the wellbeing economy with the National Strategy for Economic Transformation (2022) citing a wellbeing economy as the Scottish Government's economic vision: "a society that is thriving across economic, social and environmental dimensions" and reducing inequalities (Scottish Government, 2022: 4).

This multidimensional and broad-based perspective on the economy, and what 'counts' as measures of success, is accompanied by the view that several types of assets or 'capitals' which reflect the strengths of individuals and societies, natural resources, and more traditional economic and business characteristics are required to deliver sustainable wellbeing (Scottish Government, 2020). As we recognise below, the notion of 'assets' has appeared in many concepts and frameworks, but the geographical distribution of many foundational resources is unclear (MacKinnon et al., 2021) and as established indicators of deprivation should be interpreted carefully and supplemented with other knowledge in rural areas (Clelland and Hill, 2019), creating new evidence on access to assets at the local level could be highly valuable in informing improved development approaches.

How can we use assets to understand local development?

To define the conceptual framework for our 'assets inventory', we have searched across diverse bodies of literature to identify potential approaches for framing local development around assets. First, the literature on community capitals focuses explicitly on the resources available to a community as the starting point for local economic and human development. A notable example of these frameworks is the Scottish Government's 'Four Capitals' approach (Advisory Group on Economic Recovery, 2020: 18), which identifies four fundamental pillars in order to track progress towards its wellbeing economy goals:

Environment, or Natural Capital; People, or Human Capital; Community, or Social Capital; and Business, or Economic Capital.

Another such framework is proposed by Flora (2009) and Flora et al. (2018), who provide a similar, but more detailed, classification of community capitals, intended as an “organizational frame for understanding the diversity and changes in rural communities” (Flora et al., 2018: XV). Their framework envisions community capitals as classified into six distinct yet strongly interconnected types: Natural Capital, Cultural Capital, Human Capital, Social Capital, Political Capital, Financial Capital, and Built Capital. This approach stresses the interconnectedness of the capitals, recognising that capitals contribute both individually and together to a community’s sustainable development. Due to this, “achieving sustainability requires balance among the capitals” (Flora et al. 2018: 16).

Furthermore, there is an extensive body of literature exploring alternative approaches to economic development – some of these approaches include pathways to “wellbeing-focused” and “foundational” economies. As these literatures are partly concerned with finding novel ways to measure progress towards development goals (beyond mainstream indicators of economic growth, such as Gross Domestic Product), they emphasise the role of different components of the economy to enhance individual and collective wellbeing, particularly on a local scale. An example of these approaches is the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development’s Regional Wellbeing framework (Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development, 2011), which aims to assess local wellbeing under multiple dimensions – material living conditions, as well as quality of life and subjective wellbeing. With a similar goal but different approach, the foundational economy literature proposes to focus on “the part of the economy that creates and distributes goods and services consumed by all (regardless of income and status) because they support everyday life” (Bentham et al., 2013: 7). This includes material services, which are tied to physical infrastructure (such as utilities, transportation, telecommunication, food production and distribution), and providential services, tied to human-to-human interaction (mostly welfare services, such as healthcare, education and social care). Under this framework, wellbeing is linked to the social consumption of these essential goods and services, which, by their nature, are provided and consumed locally; therefore, these economic activities are key drivers of development – in other words, ‘assets’ – for the communities where they take place.

Other frameworks not considered within this report, but which form important learning, include asset-based community development, which focuses on the existing capacities and skills within a community as the starting point for all development pathways (Kretzmann and McKnight, 1996), and neo-endogenous development, which emphasises the importance of blending top-down and bottom-up approaches to local development through negotiation between local and extra-local actors (Bosworth et al., 2016).

These frameworks highlight the multiple approaches to defining and distinguishing between types of assets. However, it is also critical to consider insights from practitioners and stakeholders involved in delivering rural economic development, and the expertise of rural researchers, in prioritising what should be measured going forward in this research. These aspects are described in the following section, including a summary in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Information contributing to the structure and content of the assets inventory

Our next step has been to enrich the conceptual frameworks outlined above with the expertise of external stakeholders and practitioners involved in different aspects of rural economic development across Scotland. We started by compiling a comprehensive directory of relevant organisations, predominantly identified through a range of initial sources (including national and regional strategies, government reports, information on city region deals, and other documents mentioning stakeholder organisations). For each stakeholder organisation we recorded the sector(s) in which it operates, then proceeded to condense all sectors into 10 unique 'macrosectors', assigning each organisation to one:

- Environment
- Agrifood sector and land-based activities
- Land
- Culture
- Health, mental health, wellbeing
- Community outcomes
- Housing, energy, transport
- Economic development
- Human capital
- Advocacy

From this directory, we selected organisations (evenly distributed across the different macrosectors) and proceeded to invite key contacts from each organisation to two online workshops (held in February 2023) where we asked the question "What assets are needed by rural and island communities to enable a wellbeing-focused recovery?". Seventeen experts and practitioners, representing an equal number of stakeholder organisations, attended the workshops (out of a total of 39 that were initially invited). In these workshops, participants were asked to discuss and identify potential 'assets', which were defined very

broadly as “the resources that characterise a place and the people that live there, which can benefit the local community and businesses in some way”, with the ‘Four Capitals’ presented as a prompt (but not a guide) for ideas and discussion. All participants’ interventions were compiled onto an online whiteboard, which was later extracted and analysed using text mining methods. The assets provided within the table below represent frequently occurring pairs of words (bigrams) in transcribers’ virtual sticky notes, which reflect what was discussed by workshop participants.

Furthermore, insights from two other research activities being undertaken in the wider project have contributed to a long list of assets. Firstly, three questionnaires were being finalised to collect data on the nature of public decision-making on key economic issues, with the intention of identifying the factors and issues which form barriers and opportunities for:

- people's movement to and from rural regions in Scotland;
- the development of resilient local food systems in rural areas;
- providing sustainable and affordable rural transport

Characteristics or ‘attributes’ used in previous studies on these topics were identified from detailed literature reviews, and were modified based on researcher feedback, and these are noted in the inventory alongside the subjects of decision-making. Secondly, researchers intend to develop an advanced agent-based model encompassing the rural economy, communities and the environment, which will integrate data and insights generated from quantitative and qualitative research, forming an advanced tool to potentially simulate the impacts and outcomes in rural Scotland from potential shocks, events and policy changes. As part of this research, two multidisciplinary brainstorming sessions have been held in 2023 within the Hutton-based project teams on the rural economy and rural communities projects, to identify the potential scope of an agent-based model. These have generated a 'mind map' containing a network of the elements, attributes, links and processes which, based on researcher experience and expertise, are within the scope of Scotland's rural economy, communities and the environment. A model structure will be informed by these discussions, but the preliminary map has been assessed to identify main and sub-categories of assets within the network. Main categories of assets are included in the inventory below.

The assets inventory is summarised in Table 1, illustrating (as rows) the different assets and the sources where they were mentioned. For the recent learning from stakeholders and practitioners which specifically addressed the links between assets and a wellbeing-focused rural recovery, the thematic links are shown between these assets and domains (in columns) within three frameworks highlighted in the literature review:

- the 'Four Capitals' of assets which support a wellbeing economy (Scottish Government, 2020, 2022);
- the alternative framing of community capitals proposed by Flora et al. (2018);
- the material and providential services which form aspects of the foundational economy (Bentham et al., 2013)

It is important to note that this cross-tabulation is preliminary and exploratory in nature, and that this has not been pursued for the other sources which have contributed to the inventory, partly as these are not presently finalised. Additionally, only the main categories and attributes from the latter two sources are given below, for clarity.

Table 1: Assets inventory

Asset	Four Capitals				Community capitals							Foundational economy	
	Environment / Natural Capital	People / Human Dimension	Community / Social Capital	Business / Economic Capital	Natural capital	Cultural capital	Human capital	Social capital	Political capital	Financial capital	Built capital	Material services	Providential services
Stakeholder and practitioner expertise: assets needed by rural and island communities to enable a wellbeing-focused recovery													
Digital capacity*		✓		✓			✓				✓	✓	
Risk tolerance*		✓	✓			✓	✓	✓					
Specific mentality		✓	✓			✓	✓	✓					
Produced locally				✓							✓	✓	
Local resources	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Local priority			✓					✓	✓				
Local authority			✓					✓	✓				✓
Public sector			✓					✓	✓				✓
Affordable housing				✓							✓	✓	
Core infrastructure				✓							✓	✓	
Anchor organisation			✓					✓					✓
Statutory bodies			✓					✓	✓				✓
Capacity build		✓	✓			✓	✓	✓					
Resource allocation	✓		✓	✓	✓			✓	✓	✓		✓	✓
Community wealth building			✓	✓				✓	✓	✓		✓	✓
Community land	✓		✓	✓	✓			✓		✓			
Land fund			✓	✓						✓	✓		✓
Community schools		✓		✓			✓				✓		✓
Community ownership	✓		✓	✓	✓			✓			✓	✓	

Main categories of assets emerging from a 'mind map' of Scotland's rural economy, communities and the environment
Businesses
Adaptability
Diversification
Third sector
Community groups
Governments
Money
Funding for infrastructure
Services
Healthcare
Education
Financial services
Infrastructure
Transport
Digital & mobile
Housing (enough, affordable)
People
People who are active in the community
Working people
Volunteers
Households
Entertainment
Social activities
Culture
History
Community spirit
Jobs
Land
Weather
Landscape
Water
Green and blue spaces
Energy
Fuel being used
Attributes affecting public decision-making on economic issues, and the subjects of this decision-making to be assessed
('PM': people's movement, 'RFE': regional food economy, 'T': transport)
Different localities as potential places of residence (PM)
The quality of the natural environment (PM)
The quality of digital connectivity (PM)
Commuting time to the workplace (PM)
The distance from the family members (PM)
The distance from the closest primary school (PM)
The distance from the nearest acute hospital (PM)
The distance from the grocery shop (PM)
The location typology (PM)
The household income (PM)
Regularly purchased fresh vegetables in rural Scotland (RFE)

Place of production (RFE)
Mode of production (conventional vs organic) (RFE)
Accessibility, i.e., the distance from the point of sale (RFE)
Freshness (RFE)
Benefits to the community (certification as a “living wage employer”) (RFE)
Price (RFE)
Travel method: bike, private vehicle, public transport, on-demand transport (T)
Travel time in minutes (T)
Reliability (T)
Frequency of service (T)
Way of booking (T)
Cost of the trip (T)

*- reworded

Summary: reflections, stakeholder experience, and next steps

In addition to the experience and expertise of stakeholders with direct experience of rural development in practice, the inventory shown above (Table 1) summarises emerging insights from researchers and academic literature which are related to assets. It is important to prioritise the stakeholders’ views, as they were specifically asked to consider assets in the context of the wellbeing economy, at a point in time when disruptive events and ongoing challenges, such as the cost-of-living crisis, were affecting the economy of rural Scotland, following the COVID-19 pandemic which dominated thinking when this research was being planned. The structured summary of the assets above presents only a partial picture of the discussions which took place, although data collection in this research will be informed by the mapping of assets shown. While physical, tangible and potentially more readily 'measurable' assets were highlighted in the discussions, the factors ‘in the background’ which enable people and communities to benefit from these assets were also emphasised, including critical issues of ownership, governance, networks, and capabilities and confidence. The in-depth insights from stakeholders within these workshops will be reviewed in more detail in the future, to acknowledge the huge value of these experiences and recognise these in our research going forward. Based on the tabular summary above of assets and frameworks, the value of a broad perspective on the economy is suggested based on the number of 'economic' assets which reflect examples of human and social capital. The 'classification' of assets against dimensions of frameworks is preliminary, and is inevitably subjective, and we also reflect that the foundational economy has emerged as a potentially valuable model for considering in analysis going forward.

The next stage of this research (formally taken forward in Work Package 1) is converting the assets inventory into a fresh, spatially detailed database of rural diversity in Scotland, which will enable researchers to evaluate local-level access to diverse assets and characteristics which are drivers of broad-based economic development and recovery. These data will be published openly (as far as possible) and will support analysis and modelling in the Hutton-led projects on the rural economy and communities, with the intention that these will identify new insights into rural development, spatial inequalities, and links with community-level outcomes and changes in these over time. Specifications for ‘ideal’ levels of data quality and spatial resolution will be formulated. At present, we aspire to calculate access to assets at a highly local level, aligning with best practice in data publication within Europe (an example of which is the 1km grid square-resolution population data analysed in the Nordic countries: see Stjernberg and Penje, 2019) and overcoming the limitations of existing geographical units for understanding rural development (see Flowerdew et al., 2007). We will also identify consistent, meaningful definitions of ‘access’, applicable in different rural, small town and urban contexts, building on experience in calculating access to people based on travel times (in the definition of Sparsely Populated Areas: see Hopkins and Piras, 2020). We will

continue discussions with RESAS and the Scottish Government through established networks to support the policy relevance and responsiveness of this research to changes and events in rural Scotland.

Contact

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